

Empirical evaluation of an e-learning module for a World Heritage Listed UNESCO Monument in Cyprus: Towards the Flipped Classroom paradigm

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Abstract: One of the main challenges in the field of Digital Cultural Heritage is the use of digitized content from open repositories, such as Europeana, for education and tourism. The paper focuses on the methodology and results of the evaluation of an e-learning heritage course that re-designs such content and helps primary school students learn about an UNESCO World Heritage Listed monument in Cyprus. The aim was to develop a system that re-uses digital heritage resources in a comprehensive and user-friendly way, addressed to specific age groups, and able to fit the national educational curriculum. The main innovative feature of this project is the design of online modules adapted to monuments. To determine whether the design decisions and the content created meet user requirements, teacher's and learner's needs, a methodology of joint techniques was implemented to acquire qualitative feedback from three distinct user-groups (teachers, teaching inspectors, and students). Results show that teachers and teaching inspectors approved both the content of the e-module and its appropriateness to the particular age group. Additionally, students were enthusiastically engaged using the e-module during their History lesson, in a Flipped Classroom environment.

1. Introduction

The digitization of Cultural Heritage (CH) artefacts, e.g. historical buildings, sculptures, paintings, books etc., is becoming more and more widespread. One of the areas where use of such digitized artefacts can bear fruit is education. Arts and Heritage education can empower society's knowledge and creativity [1, 2]. When it is aligned with Information and Communications Technologies (ICT), this type of digital education can be motivating, effective, and compelling at all educational levels: from pupils to life-long learners.

In the area of Technology-supported learning, systematic effort has been put to enhance teaching and learning inside classrooms [3]. Nevertheless, it is more famously adopted in subjects such as Science, Technology, Engineering and Math (STEM), and in Higher Education, also due to the need of managing the big number of students, homework's deadlines, online rating, synchronous and asynchronous chat, and so forth [4]. In the case of online courses on History or Heritage for primary schools, much lesser research has been conducted [3]. The particular subjects, that belong to social studies, are dominated by traditional teaching approaches which focus on memorizing amounts of historical content [5], thus often obscuring the opportunity for the learner to critically engage with the content or, ideally, to enable her historical thinking. The main problem is identified in teacher's lecturing and assessing of students' recalling skills, which are time consuming and prevent interaction, collaboration, and argumentation to arise among the students and the teacher [5–7].

To that end, the Flipped Classroom (FC) model, which is a Blended Learning environment model, is designed to better allocate the classroom time by replacing traditional lectures with video lectures, liberating more time for interactive learning activities, scaffolded and personalized learning according to student's and students' needs [6], [7]. Students watch the video lecture before classroom, so the teacher has more time to discuss on the video, analyze primary or secondary historical sources with the students, and generally, promote historical thinking through hypothesis, argumentation and reflection via queries. Although the FC model has been gaining recognition and research studies investigate whether it can also improve student's self-determination [8], teachers still face technological competence since they need time and effort to design or develop digital interactive activities and video content.

This paper intends to describe the specific approach related to CH education in a blended learning environment with the use of ICT, in the form of an online course that offers interactive media to the teacher in order to enhance her teaching on an explicit topic. Its main goal is to provide feedback on the empirical evaluation of the online module through a methodology of joint techniques. The module was implemented as additional support, meaning it provided additional digital content for the teacher's lecture, for a two-hours History lesson in a primary school of Cyprus.

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3. Research and Related Work

CH education and ICT

Research on CH education through the mediation of ICT has shown that such a combination can re-define the way we perceive culture and heritage, through interactive and multisensorial learning experiences [3, 10]. CH education cannot be limited in the context of formal education. Since the early 2000s, it has been regarded that institutions associated with informal education (e.g. museums) use digital tools, advanced interfaces, and technologies, with the potential of raising public awareness and engagement with CH artefacts [11, 12]. After the expansion of internet (Web 2.0 authoring tools) and social media, museums and other heritage related institutions (galleries, libraries, etc.), started exploiting the affordances of the present ‘digital era’ in order to engage further their audiences with innovative and interactive online virtual collections and tours, including social media attributes as well [13]. Artefacts become vivid through e.g. cutting-edge virtual representations giving the visitor the capacity to interact directly with them [14], tangible user interfaces that engage children through kinesthetic interaction [15], Augmented Reality (AR) in smart phones and positioning technologies in archaeological sites [16], and other applications that take also into account accessibility issues [17], [18]. The design of these processes is oriented to deliver more involving, attractive, open, and substantial learning experiences around CH.

While the abovementioned means of informal education become purposeful, representational, and appealing thus enhancing the total visitor experience, learning about CH can take new form even in the context of formal education, namely school. Conservatively, CH education in most European school curriculums is usually affiliated with on-site visits of students and their teachers at archaeological sites, museums, and so forth [19], [20]. Students’ reflection on these visits though, should be somehow assessed. On the other hand, several studies have tried to implement advanced CH applications inside or outside the classroom to either introduce students to a historical battle [21], or provide them with an augmented representation of a ruined city [22], or let them ‘talk’ with historical figures that survived Holocaust [23], or involve them in collaborative activities and GIS mapping to re-discover their local heritage [24], or just manipulate, play, and explore [25] paintings and other CH artefacts.

With (a) the different types of multimedia offered to supplement the learning experience, (b) the emergence of online learning and (c) the concept of FC, the traditional face-to-face lessons can evolve dramatically, and therefore the lessons related to CH education, such as History, Visual Arts, Literature and so on.

In order to achieve a favorable learning outcome, some learning approaches that ensure the added value of ICT in CH education must be considered during design. According to [10], there are four outlined learning approaches, mainly resulting from the capability of ICT to turn CH artefacts into dynamic and interactive representations, which also constitute our system’s requirements. Those are: (1) Personalized, inquiry-based learning approaches; (2) On-site and anywhere learning experiences; (3) Interdisciplinary learning approaches; and (4) Collaborative learning experiences. In section *Online learning platform*, is presented how we managed to reach those four learning approaches in our system.

Target groups

The two featured modules of the online learning platform have been considered for various age groups: from kids to teenagers, to adult, professionals and life-long learners. CH education can apply to any of these age groups. Due to the variety of our audience, virtual teachers to accompany each module have been added. Depending on the age of the users, different heritage data, games, and textual information are customized [26]. Hence, the virtual teachers have been introduced to improve the UX (i.e. the educator identifies easily, and quickly which module is appropriate for her classroom) and the organization of the modules. Our under-evaluation module *Timios Stavros Pelendria*, which represents a church with simple structure, unfussy architectural elements and building phases than the module *Panagia Asinou*, is addressed to students between 6 – 12 years old (*Fig. 1*). In accordance, the evaluation of the particular online module involved stakeholders relevant to primary school students and Cypriot primary school curriculum.

4. Goals and Methodology

The design of the online learning platform, and by extension the online module, followed an iterative design approach by a multidisciplinary research team of designers, an architect, an electrical engineer, a teacher and an instructional designer specialized on History and Culture. The first phase was quite short. It included research and inquiry related to the purpose of the project: the use and re-design of specific digitized heritage data in a way that the information is educative for the people: grown-ups and children. This phase focused on fast brainstorming and a combination of proposed methodologies in the respective fields of ICT and CH education. The middle phase was design and prototyping: a responsive online learning platform with two pilot modules (wp.digitalheritage-lab.eu). The last phase of the design approach included empirical evaluation and testing with semi-structured interviews, online questionnaire, and in-situ observation in one of the featured pilot courses.

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TEACHER: MRS DANAE

Danae teaches children 6 to 12 years old

> TEACHERS > TEACHER: MRS DANAE

About Mrs. Danae

She teaches at elementary schools the last 12 years. Her students are usually between 6 and 12 years old. She is experienced and loves to interact with the children. She also helps children with learning difficulties to participate and interact at the class. In this online course she is the teacher of the following monuments:

1. Timios Stavros (Holy Cross)
2. Panagia Moutoulla
3. Monastery of Agios Ioannis
4. Timios Stavros Agiasmati

She is the favourite teacher of young children and they all love her!

Fig. 1. Example of the virtual teacher that ‘accompanies’ the featured online course “Timios Stavros Pelendria”. Screenshot © from <https://wp.digitalheritagelab.eu/teachers/mrs-danae/> (last accessed 29.01.19)

The four learning approaches that guarantee the added value of ICT in CH education, form the system’s requirements and they are analyzed in two separate sections. The section *Online learning platform* includes the overall design decisions. The section *Online module: Timios Stavros Pelendria* covers the organization of content that was included in both pilot modules, and the selection of the final design elements for the module *Timios Stavros Pelendria*.

A number of design constrains and project’s goals, that will be later assessed in the 5. Evaluation phase, have been taken under consideration. For instance, the presentation of the content and the navigation map of the online learning platform and the module, could play leading roles in successful usability. Nevertheless, the most challenging issue in this project is mostly related to the usefulness of the online module itself when it is used inside classroom by teachers, to provide a more socio constructivist [27], [28] learning environment. In addition, the content must also fit the national educational curriculum, must be flexible to be used similarly to other related lessons (Visual Arts, Language, Literature, etc.), and must be didactically effective [29], [30].

Online learning platform

As stated in [26], each monument is presented in the form of an online module addressed to different age group. One important design aspect was that our system should be able to run in every smart device (Android, iPhone, iPad, Windows tablets, etc.) to fulfill *on-site and everywhere learning experiences*. Then, users would be able to visit an online module while being actually at its featured monument. Consequently, the system’s design followed the “Bring Your Own Device” (BYOD) tactic, which also encompasses *personalized learning* though *inquiry-based approaches* [31], [32]. To achieve these, a responsive web site was developed, capable of running on desktop and portable devices. An Educational Theme (WordPress) with CSS reconfiguration was selected, because its User Interface (UI) is similar to the most popular online learning platforms on the internet e.g. Coursera, Udacity, edX, and the users are already familiar with it (Fig. 2). This way, a central User Experience (UX) requirement is covered.

Gamified aspects (puzzles, knowledge quizzes) and material related content, such as the included 3D models of the monuments, are offered inside the modules to be used creatively either by learners themselves or by teachers inside school context. For example, students could be separated in teams completing a featured puzzle game, or they could 3D-print the model of the church and then touch, interact, and paint it collaboratively. In this way, the teacher is provided with interactive media assets which, when properly integrated, can evolve to *collaborative learning experiences*. When they are combined with lessons like Painting and Visual Arts, or Sociology, or Religious, they could even promote *interdisciplinary learning approaches*. In both pilot modules, emphasis has been given to the local history of the monuments and resources related to Cypriot Archaeology and Antiquity, in order to encourage further exploitation by other associated disciplines and professors. Supplementary, location on google maps and visiting information about the featured monuments are also provided inside the modules, so students and teachers can effortlessly organize their educational excursions.

Online module: Timios Stavros Pelendria

The module has a number of lessons. The information about the monument is divided as seen in Fig. 2, right:

1. Introduction: lesson about the History of the Monument.

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2. Lesson about the Local History: short reference on the local history through the literature study.
3. Video: short dramatized video
4. Glossary: important words that are used at the text.
5. The 3D object (downloadable in a pdf file and in a simple online version).
6. Comprehension questions.
7. Activities: puzzles, hotspot images, games.
8. Quiz: a short quiz (usually 10-20 Questions) about the Monument. You need to score 70% in order to pass.
9. References: resources and links for further studying

In every lesson, there is time estimation to help the learner follow her own pace while studying. It is also helpful for the teacher to follow a scaffolded time allocation, so she can better manage time and assign any remaining lessons as homework to students. At the end of the module, there is a “Review” section, where every user can write a review and /or choose between a 1-5 stars scale. High-scored modules will then be presented at the Home Page.

Fig. 2. The UI of the e-module “Timios Stavros Pelendria”.

Screenshot © from <https://wp.digitalheritagelab.eu/shop/church-of-timos-stavros-holy-cross-pelendria/> (last accessed 29.01.19)

In order for the students to engage with the historical and architectural content of the church, a dramatized video is presented in every module. Its purpose is to narrate descriptively and communicatively the key elements that everyone should know about the monument. Scenario and subtitling are formed in simple terms according to the target audience. A simplified glossary is also provided to help the learner highlight all the possible unknown words related with unfamiliar vocabulary or a discipline’s terminology (e.g. architecture). The 3D object is offered in 3D pdf file, which was chosen as the most common, accessible, and easy-to-run 3D file format. A colorful and meaningful fresco of the church is used as a puzzle game (Fig. 3), where the students are most likely to interact with it and get to know it through a more joyful and gamified way. Finally, comprehension questions, a quiz where you can also share its results, as well as additional sources at the end of the module, have been added for reflection and further investigation.

5. Evaluation

The described system model aims to respond to the contemporary pedagogical directions and its users’ needs. To investigate whether these requirements are met, a methodology of joint techniques was implemented to three (3) potential user groups. The pedagogical issues should be evaluated in association with experts in education, experts in the learning domain, and inside school context. For that reason, the evaluation procedure received consensus from the Ministry of Education and Culture of Cyprus (Application number 182225) providing all the necessary requirements to conduct research associated with our user groups: informed consent, understanding of the opportunities provided by the research, confidentiality, anonymity and non-traceability, reliability and validity. The module is also offered in Greek language.

Fig. 3. Screenshot from the featured puzzle game. This plugin offers the player additional, helpful elements. Elements at the bottom (from left to right): see the complete image, transparent the complete image at the background, arrange or disarrange pieces, settings menu, completion percentage, time passed, play on the forum (Jigsaw planet), full screen view. Screenshot © from <https://wp.digitalheritagelab.eu/shop/church-of-timios-stavros-holy-cross-pelendria/> (last accessed 29.01.19)

Methods and Participants

The main purpose of the evaluation was to acquire both quantitative (to some extent) and qualitative feedback from our user groups. Three crucial elements should be assessed: the ones that also led to conceptualization and design of the online learning platform:

1. Level of engagement of the students;
2. Scientific integrity of the content;
3. Usability of the online learning platform /module, when used in school context.

Three pairs of *user group - evaluation method* (Table 1) were assigned according to the type of user and the quantity /quality of data needed to be obtained from each type:

Table 1. The pairs of *user group-evaluation method* assigned depending on what to be ‘measured’

To be assessed	User group	Method
Level of engagement	Students	In-site observation
Scientific integrity of content	Teaching inspectors	Semi-structured interviews
Usability of the online module	Teachers	(online) Questionnaire

In-site Observation

A formal educational setting, where the teacher introduces the subject to her students with the support of the online module to alter their learning experience using different, more interactive, and multimodal means than traditional lecturing, is a favorable use-case scenario for our online learning platform. Such an environment encourages the emergence of the ordinary interactions and the already shaped ‘chemistry’ among the students and their teacher. Hence, they can express freely their ideas and thoughts, agreements or disagreements with the opinions or attitudes of their peers and the teacher.

These rich forms of interaction and qualitative data were anticipated in order to understand (i) *how the online module can perform as an educational tool in the hands of the teacher and towards students’ motives*, (ii) *in what ways students are engaged*, and (iii) *how the teacher uses supportively the online module (e.g. video, mini quiz) to increase the engagement of her students*.

Seventeen (17) students, 11 years old, of the 5th grade of the 4th Primary school of Limassol (KV) in Cyprus were observed inside their classroom while using the online module *Timios Stavros Pelendria*. All students were familiar with technology and had used PCs in classroom before. The majority of the students had not come across with online modules or MOOCs before. During the evaluation procedure, a camera was used to monitor the process as well as notes on inquiries posed by students. The lesson started with the teacher introducing the topic while the students seated in teams of two and one team of three, in front of a desktop (Fig. 4). The teacher used an interactive board to display the online module and followed the sequence of the lessons as they are presented in Fig. 2, right. The dramatized video could not be assigned as homework before classroom, as it is supposed in a FC environment. However, because not all the students were able to stream it from their home, the video played inside classroom.

Semi-structured interviews

Interviews are principally prevalent and effective in the case of qualitative surveys. In this research, semi-structured interviews were employed to inform on (i) *the authenticity of the content*, (ii) *the appropriateness of the way it is presented*, (iii) and *the overall approach of the platform*. Three (3) teaching inspectors specialized in Arts' education, Literature, and Culture were interviewed around central questions about the online learning module concerning its:

- (a) alignment with the Cypriot primary school curriculum,
- (b) flexibility to be used as supporting tool for other lessons as well,
- (c) usefulness during classroom lectures, and
- (d) didactic effectiveness, according to their point of view and experience.

All three of them had access to the platform and browsed its modules. Questions were formed in a way that they could be slightly changed or evolved depending on the answers given by the interviewees, in order to serve the purpose of an interview and not of a questionnaire. This method is also helpful when the interviewee is capable and proficient to provide researchers not only with feedback, but also with helpful insights and ideas about re-design and future perspectives of the platform, as in this case.

Fig. 4. Students completing the featured quiz in teams of two during in-site observation.

Online questionnaire

Teachers, comparing to teaching inspectors, are the experts in the learning domain with a special insight, as they face more often problems related to successful lecturing, time management during a lecture, availability of digital resources and interactive media, students' management and aspects of their way of learning, engagement, and general behavior. The questionnaire aimed to inform the researcher on the same issues as the *Semi-structured interviews*, but more massively and more precisely, focusing again on usefulness, usability, and didactic effectiveness of the online module.

The aim was to create a short, focused, and easy to use tool, able to be answered in 5 minutes by a wide number of teachers in Cyprus, providing also the hyperlink to browse the online learning platform and the module. Questions were on basic functionality criteria, such as the structure of the course and time allocation between lessons. The online questionnaire was sent via *Google Forms*¹ to a sample of approximately 200 primary school teachers all over Cyprus, where only 28 of them answered it completely.

Results and Discussion

In-site Observation

The classroom lesson lasted for almost two hours, as the teacher exhausted all the time proposed by the online module, adding also her own questions, opening parallel discussions and building on the pre-existing knowledge of her students. This is an aspect that can be controlled generally by the teacher, since it is her who knows her students' weaknesses, the limit of their proximal development along with their pace and capabilities to handle

¹ https://www.google.com/intl/el_gr/forms/about/ (accessed 01/09/2018)

new knowledge. At the end of the lesson, a 5-minutes brief -but enlightening- discussion was followed, between the students and their Arts' teacher describing their experience with this new type of lecturing.

The highlighted outcomes of the specific evaluation method are that students (1) paid attention on the paintings, frescoes, and their representations, (2) they expressed their interest to visit the church and the online module after the lesson, and (3) they commented that it was delightful to have both the introductory text and the dramatized video.

The first outcome was surprising because the research team, during the *research and inquiry* phase, had not anticipated that the HQ images at the beginning of the module could have triggered students' curiosity. As soon as the teacher realized that students could understand and identify the differences in the styles depicted in the frescoes that resulted from two different painters in different time periods of the decoration of the church (historical facts at the introductory text), she devoted more time discussing on the theme. A challenge rises for the design team to implement particular interactions or inquiry-based mini games or quizzes about the frescoes and their dissimilar styles. In addition, the word "style" in Greek (=τεχνοτροπία), is a word that students of that age are not familiar with, that is why the word belonged also to the *glossary* session. Nevertheless, they spent time on identifying significant differences in the styles (colors, forms) while also analyzing the word "τεχνοτροπία" with their teacher, hence at some point they started using the word more and more correctly and when appropriate. This is a tiny but, at the same time, important aspect of a critical constructive combination that includes observation, analysis, and reflection both on the use of the word and the observed historical resources (frescoes in this case), which students came to make after the didactic intervention.

Second, the fact that students expressed interest to visit the online module again, indicates that the whole presentation of the content and the final learning experience was engaging and effective. On the other hand, the expression of interest to visit the featured church is a positive sign that the online module and the lecture had an impact on their cultural awareness. Firstly, they got to know about the specific monument, which was unknown to most of them at the time, and secondly, they got interested to visit it either with their families or school. Last but not least, students commented that they liked the video and the comment that "*the dramatized video completed the first textual information about the history of the church*", made by the most outstanding student of the classroom, were evidence that the video had fulfilled its purpose: repetition of the key elements of the monument in the form of a story, communicative, and appealing. The last two outcomes resulted from the concluding brief discussion of the students with their Arts' teacher, who had clear and targeted questions, wrapping up students' experience with the online module and helping us improve the total image of this two-hours lecture.

Semi-structured interviews

Semi-structured interviews' resulting answers were contradicting, thus truly constructive and productive for the research team. All of them approved the authenticity of the content and its scientific integrity as well as its appropriateness for ages 10-11 years old (5th and 6th grade), and the fact that it can build on the pre-existing knowledge of the students. Moreover, they all think that the online module is a valuable tool in the hands of the teacher, easy to learn and use, but it still needs to involve additional pedagogical approaches.

The first interviewee characterized the pedagogical approach of the online module as 'teacher-centered'. He expressed his eagerness for more creative content to be added in the module that could trigger students' critical thinking. In addition, he mentioned that a re-designed version should give more 'space' to students to investigate and create themselves new content from the existing one. Furthermore, to reflect on more cultural heritage related issues via the quizzes and not only on the knowledge or the information acquired, as in this provided quiz. He could definitely exploit it during a Visual Arts' lesson and gave also a beautiful creative idea to make an art exhibition using the 3D printed model of the church as a canvas where the students would paint divided in teams, showcasing aspects of its use in the village, the reason it was destroyed, and so forth. This was a quite engaging activity the research team had the opportunity to apply later in various science communication festivals that share research and ideas with the public and specially with youth.

The second interviewee, on the other side, approved the structure of the content and the time allocation between the individual lessons, although it reminds a typical teacher's centered sequence. He was able to see it employed in other lessons as well, like Religious. He also gave us specific corrections regarding some words used in the texts and some remarks, such as classifying the images at the beginning of the online module. The last interviewee stressed that the module was lacking a few more central elements for a Heritage related course. She underlined that the module needs a connection between the monument and the community or events that take place around the church and the village. Moreover, emphasis should be placed at the representations of the frescoes in order for the children to meet aspects and scenes from the life of Jesus the painters created and correlate them with other frescoes in other churches in Cyprus, their colors and dimensions. She found useful that there is a map showing the location of the church as well as an HQ image showing its outside. Relating those with the 3D model and the

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information given in the introductory text, students can realize its shape, structure, and well-preservation that enlisted *Timios Stavros* in UNESCO WHL of monuments.

Online questionnaire

Even though the sample of the primary school teachers (28) in Cyprus that completed the online questionnaire is small, it could be trustworthy as 24 out of 28 have over 10 years of experience, 16 have a masters' degree while other 4 have a PhD degree (Fig. 5). More than half believe the online learning platform provides the student with the appropriate teaching tools and those are, according to teachers, the activities, the games and the targeted questions.

As far as the scientific integrity of the content and its appropriateness to the particular age group, they all converged to positive, but as far as the question *"Is the learner's prerequisite knowledge of the content negotiated by the platform the minimum possible?"*, answers were scattered converging to *not so sure*. Maybe because the lesson involves information about constructural and decoration phases, new terminology and notions that students are not yet familiar with. On the other hand, teachers were all positive that (i) the video is an effective means of dissemination of the information it presents, (ii) the puzzle increases the engagement of the student with the presented topic given her age, and (iii) the reflective quiz is adequate to the educational level of the learner. According to the usability of the platform inside a classroom's lesson, teachers' answers were scattered around positive degrees (Fig. 5). They believe that (a) its individual features and navigation are easy to learn and access, (b) the teacher is encouraged by the proposed distribution of time at the distinct learning sessions, and (c) also encouraged by exploring additional sources (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Indicative results from the online questionnaire.

6. Conclusions

This paper focuses on the methodology and results of the evaluation of a CH digital online course. The online module is hosted in an online learning platform that helps users learn about two UNESCO WHL monuments in

Cyprus: their history and architectural value [26]. The primary objectives of the project² that brought us the platform were (a) the use of data from open repositories (such as Europeana), and (b) the development of digital tools for education on UNESCO monuments, whereas the challenge was *how to manage the variety of data, users, and devices*. The result is a responsive educational platform (wp.digitalheritagelab.eu), where every monument becomes a course addressed to different age group.

The proposed model aims to respond to the contemporary pedagogical and methodological directions of the present era, by using and blending innovative digital heritage resources to educate people of diverse ages and academic backgrounds, while it organizes ICT into four main axes. To determine whether the design decisions and the content created meet user's requirements, teacher's and learner's needs, a formative evaluation of the online module addressed to primary school learners took place in a fully educational context. Three methods were implemented:

- (a) in-site observation for our main target group, in the form of a school lesson inside classroom: seventeen (17) students, aged 10-11, with their teacher as mediator;
- (b) semi-structured interviews for our expert users: three (3) teaching inspectors, and
- (c) questionnaires for our bigger sample of users: twenty-eight (28) Cypriot primary school teachers.

Teachers and teaching inspectors, which are the experts in our case and two potential user groups of our online learning platform, informed us on the pedagogical usability and didactic effectiveness both of the platform and the module, via questionnaires and semi-structured interviews respectively. Students, the third user group, were observed while using the online module and its multimedia functions inside their classroom, during a History lesson introduced by their teacher. Rich forms of interaction and dialogue were recorded. In combination with the feedback from the interviews and the questionnaires, this methodology provided the first critical review of (i) the changes that should be made in the platform regarding usability and content, (ii) the elements that caught users' attention, (iii) future design directions and encouragement to develop further monument-courses or adopt the inception of the idea to other projects related to CH education.

The joint techniques used in the evaluation helped us realize the current pedagogical needs, expressed by the primary school teachers and the teaching inspectors, that require the involvement in two main didactic approaches to ensure didactic effectiveness, according to the national school curriculum as well. Those are (A) *attitudes and behaviors*, meaning the pedagogical reflection needed not only on the knowledge acquirement but also on critical topics that arise relative to CH and its preservation and protection, through dialogues, collaborative activities, and creative expressions, and (B) *21st century skills*, meaning the achievement of technological maturity by the students to implement and use digital tools in order to facilitate and empower their intellectual and personal development.

In this approach, combinatorial methods were used as suggested in [33], in order to help overcome the persistence with one technique that usually misrepresents or influences the researcher on the general image of the dealing subject. In addition, this evaluation approach is considered more as a process through which "*designers could gain full awareness of the pedagogical rationale underlying their design choices*" [34]–[37], and it is strongly believed that this approach will get closer to a mixed *user and learner-centered design* approach [30]. The challenge raised concerns the implementation of more effective didactic tools that safeguard the connection between the critical reflection on the presented issue, using the provided knowledge and information, as well as the appropriate digital skills that will enhance the process of this reflection.

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² <http://www.europeana-space.eu/archaeology-in-cyprus-demonstrator/> (last accessed 01/09/2018)

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